

Lipoma over plantar aspect of foot: An uncommon site for a common lump

Kunal Chowdhary*, Muzzafar Zaman^{*,1}, Gurinder Kaur*, Aliya Shah*, Rahul Yadav*, Ashish Chowdhary* and Ivan Inkov**

*Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana, India., **Clinic of Thoracic Surgery, Military Medical Academy, Sofia, Bulgaria.

ABSTRACT

Lipomas are the most common benign soft tissue tumour of the body, but their presence at uncommon sites like sole make those cases interesting. We present here one such case in which symptomatic swelling over the sole of the right foot was excised, and histopathology confirmed it to be a benign lipoma.

KEYWORDS Foot lipoma; Benign; a Universal tumour

INTRODUCTION

Lipoma is the most common benign soft tissue tumour found in the body, but still, its occurrence over the sole is relatively uncommon. It is known as a universal tumour [1] Lipoma is composed of mature fat cells. They are most commonly found in areas of abundant adipose tissue, which may explain why they are rarely found in the areas like sole. [2] We present a case of lipoma over the plantar aspect of the right foot.

CASE REPORT

A 32 year-old female presented to the outpatient department of our institute with a single painful swelling over the plantar aspect of the right foot. She first noticed it two years back, and it progressively increased in size and now for the past three months had started hurting her while walking. On examination, around 5 x 5 cm single well circumscribed swelling seen over the sole of right foot with overlying skin normal. The swelling was soft in consistency and well mobile from side to side and on palpation was mildly tender. USG swelling was suggestive of a soft tissue swelling. A presumptive diagnosis of lipoma foot was made, and the patient was taken for excision & biopsy. Operative finding being 5x5 cm single well-circumscribed swelling

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¹Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana, India; muzzafarzaman@yahoo.com

Figure 1: Swelling on sole right foot.

Figure 2: Swelling dissected of the plantaris tendon.

Figure 3: View post swelling dissection.

Figure 4: Excised swelling.

Figure 5: Final sutured wound.

seen over the sole of the right foot in the superficial plane above the plantaris tendon. Swelling was removed entirely and wound closed. HPE report was suggestive of benign lipoma. Sutures were removed on the 14th day and on follow up patient asymptomatic.

DISCUSSION

Lipomas occurring in the sole have been rarely reported due to the less amount of adipose tissue in the sole. They are characterized by their slow and asymptomatic evolution, which delays their diagnosis. [3] However the occurrence of lipomas in sole can be incapacitating to the patient as normal activities like walking will be affected. [4] Although a presumptive diagnosis is typically made clinically, those tumors with atypical clinical features may require radiological investigation like ultrasound and M.R.I which is regarded as gold standard investigation for soft tissue tumours. [5] Difficulty arises when radiographic features are not typical of lipoma and differentiation of lipoma variants (e.g., spindle cell lipoma, atypical lipoma, pleomorphic lipoma, lipoblastoma, angiolipoma) from liposarcoma based on imaging features is not possible, necessitating surgical resection for definitive histological diagnosis. Surgical excision remains the only treatment available currently. [6]

CONCLUSION

Lipoma though a common disease has been reported at uncommon sites like sole creating confusion in the minds of treating doctors. Knowledge of the occurrence of this swelling at these uncommon sites make life easy for patients and treating doctors.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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